

LEVELS OF STUDY OF SCIENTIFIC RESEARCH WORKS ON THE PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF PRIMARY CLASS TEACHERS BASED ON INDEPENDENT EDUCATION

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Abstract. *This article presents researches by scientists on the research levels of scientific and research work on the professional competence of primary school teachers based on independent education.*

Keywords. *scientific research, competence, individuality, qualification, variant program, information technologies.*

In world educational and scientific research institutions, researches are being conducted on improving the professional and methodical competence of future elementary school teachers on the basis of independent education, modeling and standardization of the educational process, and developing professional qualities and competencies. In this regard, on the basis of independent education, it is necessary to improve the professional and methodical competence of future elementary school teachers and to carry out professional training based on international qualification requirements, to raise the quality of education to the international level, to implement modular education. Attention is being paid to scientific researches on the activation of learning, social communication, and determination of the professionalism of primary school teachers.

The main goals of students from independent education are the following: mastering the methods of acquiring knowledge, being able to independently analyze processes; Consolidation, deepening, expansion and regulation of the knowledge acquired in classroom training [24; p. 28]; learning to work with legal acts, information and special literature; independent study of educational materials; development of activity, knowledge acquisition, creative initiative, responsibility and order; formation of the ability to apply the acquired knowledge in practice; independent thinking, self-development, formation of the implementation of one's own plan; to develop the ability to do research [24; p. 28].

S.A. Boltaboev said that training in the educational auditorium could not fully meet the requirements of high-level knowledge. In doing this, independent educational activity serves as a complementary and developmental task. In addition, independent activity serves to implement the formation of knowledge, skills and abilities defined in the subject curriculum and must be mastered by the student. [17-p]. Due to the nature of the science, independent works are developed for each type of work. Independent works [16; 18-p.] implementation and advantages and features of independent education, methodology of formation of skills from scientists, O.N. Sultanova's methodology of organizing independent educational activity of students in physics, formation of independent educational activity of students by Sh.Yunusova, Z.Nishonova, J.Tohirova and N.Khalilov's research on independent education forms was considered. The research work of S.Matjonov, the editor-in-chief, is devoted to the organization of students' independent work, in which the issues of organization of students' oral and written creative work in the lessons were studied. After all, creative work and independent activity in the formation of a morally mature generation require independent thinking. A student who did not have independent thinking, his

own point of view could not be creative, could not do independent activity. Higher education system [16; 19-p]. O.Kuysinov "In his scientific work on improving the interest and ability to learn independently in the future bachelor teachers who received education in the field of vocational education, he touched on the methods of independent learning" [138; 22-b]. According to N.A.Muslimov, independent education is an important factor in becoming a professional [20]. This is especially evident in the vocational training system.

Modern independent education

- 1. Digital technologies**
- 2. Transforming education**
- 3. Teacher-disciple (eastern traditions)**
- 4. Technology development**
- 5. Change of surroundings**
- 6. Change in communication**

1. Digital technologies are in S.I.Kulmamatov's scientific research, the organization of independent education is shown on the example of the science of informatics and information technologies, including the increase in teaching efficiency in the organization of independent education in the science of informatics and information technologies, the development of organizational pedagogical criteria, the content of tasks for independent work and their fulfillment the preparation of methodical developments is mentioned. the purpose of the research is to create computer programs for independent study of informatics and information technology students and to determine their knowledge shown.

L.B.Akhmedova spoke about the development of didactic methodical competence of future elementary school teachers in monologic and dialogic speech. The model for the development of didactic methodological competence of future elementary school teachers worked on the basis of intensive correction of creativity, communication competence, and literary pronunciation skills. In D.M.Malikova's dissertation work, spiritual value, intellectual approach and positive worldview forms are revealed in the development of reading culture of students.

The goal of N.G.Alavutdinova's mother tongue lessons is to create a methodology for developing students' creative thinking skills. Among them, the features of step-by-step preparation for written works are revealed in the mother tongue classes, the skills of independent creative writing, strengthening creative thinking.

I.B.Utaeva gave recommendations on the development of students' grammatical competences in the process of independent education, and mentioned the use of the value-semantic method of self-development and generalization of grammatical competences in students. The purpose of the research is to develop the pedagogical process of syntactic and didactic possibilities of written texts through grammatical competences

2. Transforming education is in research of A.Yu.Uvarov implements the digital transformation of fundamentally improving the quality of education, because if the educational system of the digital society meets the requirements and opportunities, the digital transformation of the society will lead to the digital economy.

3. Teacher-disciple (eastern traditions) Sh.U.Nurillaeva's methods of teaching students to observe independent thinking in primary class mother tongue lessons are widely covered, in which the ideas of Eastern scholars are effectively used, including in the works of Abu Nasr Farabi,

he says that "a person acquires knowledge through intelligence and perception". Think about independent observation in KAYKOVUS pamphlets.

4. Technology development

According to U.Azizov independent education is a form of education and it is called directed learning. Independent education is an educational activity that is carried out without supervision in some cases. Independent study is an opportunity for students to explore their interests in depth. Another way to learn independently is to understand distance learning. Distance learning is when the student is physically or mentally away from the teacher, and the student and teacher are connected by something like a worksheet, essay, or website on the Internet. Education is useful for self-study and independent scientific activity, which allows the student to be independent.

5. Change of surroundings

A.T.Mamadaliyev said that Technology (technique - art, skill,) is a tool that allows a person to influence nature in the environment in order to satisfy the needs of society and people. Its main task is to ease human labor and increase labor productivity. It allows us to master the depths of the Earth, the World Ocean, and outer space through technology. Technical tools are constantly improving, new technology, new products a new technique will be created as soon as the need arises.

6. Change in communication

Communication is communication in the exchange of information between two or more people. Or: communication is a means of understanding the exchange of information in cooperative activities between people.

From the above, it can be seen that independent work is a means of organization and management of learning activities and a means of attracting students to independent learning activities.

We single out the following features as important indicators of the concept of "independent work": 1) the existence of a contract; 2) student's lack of direct participation in the task; 3) the existence of a time specially provided for this purpose; 4) indirect management of the student's learning activity by the teacher.

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